

Improving Copernicus forecasts of Arctic sea ice and icebergs with the ACCIBERG project

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Abstract. The Arctic Ocean will always be treacherous in spite of its rapid warming. Sea ice and icebergs remain major risks for navigation in Arctic waters; therefore, monitoring and forecasting them is crucial. While the Copernicus Marine and Climate Change Services can provide the necessary information, users may not benefit from it as intended due to both a lack of consistency and missing uncertainty estimates. The EU-funded ACCIBERG project will address these issues. It will develop a new iceberg forecast service using remote sensing algorithms, data assimilation and cloud computing to consistently offer probabilistic sea ice and iceberg forecasts based on Copernicus data. The new forecasts will be automated and used by various groups navigating in the Arctic – from fisheries to cruise tourism.

Keywords. Sea ice, iceberg, probabilistic, forecasting, data assimilation, Copernicus Services.

1. Introduction

Sea ice and icebergs are a major security risk for navigation and fisheries in Arctic waters. Both will remain a significant threat even in a warmer Arctic, where maritime traffic is expected to increase. Sea Ice Services are needed more and more to support less experienced captains with automated high quality forecasts and new information about icebergs that are not available today.

To monitor and forecast sea-ice types and icebergs, adequate forecasts of sea ice, ocean, wind, and wave conditions for the whole Arctic are crucial. The Copernicus Marine and Climate Change Services provide such information products. However, their uncertainties are not provided in a consistent and user-friendly manner. Reliable uncertainty estimates can however be based on forecast ensembles across the two Copernicus Services.

ACCIBERG will improve the quality of sea ice and ocean nowcast and forecast products and their uncertainty estimates in both Copernicus Services. It will also extend the spatial coverage of the satellite detection of icebergs and develop a completely new iceberg forecast service. ACCIBERG will build upon state-of-the-art sea-ice and ocean models,

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remote sensing algorithms, data assimilation and cloud computing to offer consistent probabilistic sea-ice and iceberg forecasts based on Copernicus data. National or commercial sea-ice services are limited to smaller regions and will benefit from the increased accuracy and consistency across the Copernicus products.

The new forecasts will be demonstrated in ACCIBERG by European Ice Services and ships of opportunity. The new iceberg forecasts will be automated and validated, and benefit a wide range of user groups navigating in the Arctic, from fisheries to cruise tourism, including maritime surveillance under the Copernicus Security Service. We will provide prototype products ready to be implemented in the Copernicus services and accessible from a single entry point: its inherent cloud computing solution WeKEO.

2. Calibration of probabilistic sea-ice forecasts

2.1. Sub-seasonal to seasonal forecasts

These types of forecasts are routinely provided by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). To improve user uptake of these forecasts, ACCIBERG is developing prototypes of forecast products that are calibrated and include uncertainty estimates. We have developed an initial version of a sea-Ice Calibration, vErification and Products software (ICECAP), which we tested using ECMWF sub-seasonal ensemble forecasts on the dramatic case of the rapid freeze-up of the Siberian Shelf in October/November 2021. This rapid freeze-up event took the shipping industry by surprise, leading to more than 20 ships becoming stuck in the ice. Figure 1, below, shows promising preliminary results from ICECAP: after a simple calibration for known mean errors in the forecast, a much earlier freeze-up than in previous years is correctly predicted several weeks in advance.

Figure 1: Sea-ice concentration on the Siberian Shelf for 22/10/2021 predicted 16 days in advance by the ECMWF ensemble forecast. After calibration, this forecast would have warned users of a high probability of a freeze-up happening much earlier than in previous years.

Moreover, to further improve sea-ice forecasts, ACCIBERG partners are developing stochastic modeling techniques for the ocean model NEMO [2]. In particular, uncertainties in sea-ice dynamics and ocean-sea-ice interaction are known to be large and can potentially affect sub-seasonal to seasonal predictions. At the moment, these predictions do not account for the uncertainty associated with the sea-ice modeling component. ACCIBERG will formulate and provide optimal solutions to account for the sea-ice uncertainty, with targeted application in the NEMO-SI³ modeling framework for the ECMWF seasonal prediction system, and potentially in the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) systems that rely on the NEMO ocean numerical model, such as the 30-day forecasting capability that is currently under development by the CMEMS Global Monitoring and Forecasting Center. The stochastic modulation of sea-ice parametrizations will increase the reliability of the sea-ice forecast uncertainty estimates, with potential benefits to the forecast skill scores.

2.2. *Short-range and medium-range forecasts*

The CMEMS Arctic Monitoring and Forecasting Center focuses on forecasts out to 10 days only, using both the HYCOM-CICE model [7] and the stand-alone neXtSIM-F sea-ice model [6]. ACCIBERG partners are also developing ensemble perturbation techniques targeted to short-term ice-ocean forecasting. These efforts concentrate on the representation of uncertainties in the winds, using the ECMWF ensemble forecasts as input, but also combining random perturbations based on a spectral method. Tests are ongoing to evaluate which spatial scales are most effective at exciting the relevant modes of variability of the ice-ocean system. Improved ensemble simulation techniques can also be beneficial for ensemble data assimilation techniques.

3. **Assimilation of raw satellite passive microwave sea-ice data**

Obtaining sea-ice concentration (SIC) from raw Passive Microwave (PMW) satellite data involves a complex suite of algorithms to transform the brightness temperatures (TB) measured by the satellite at several microwave frequencies (Level-1B) into SIC values first in satellite projection (Level-2) and finally in daily gridded formats (Level-3/Level-4). In this processing, some information is lost, either due to truncation of the retrievals between the zero and 100% concentrations, or because of the temporal averaging of all the inputs to an assumed daily average.

3.1. *From daily maps to individual orbits*

Recently, the assimilation of individual satellite orbit data of SIC (vs. the standard assimilation of daily maps) was developed and tested in the NFR SIRANO project (2019-2024). Parallel experiments within a regional ice-ocean forecasting system of the Barents Sea and Svalbard region revealed that the assimilation of individual SIC orbit data generally resulted in a better analysis and a better short-range forecast of the sea-ice cover, although the impact depended on the background state [1].

3.2. *From ice concentrations to brightness temperatures*

We plan to continue this work by directly assimilating Level-1B (TB) data rather than SIC. To do so requires “flying the satellite in the model” [3] and using an observation operator adapted to the satellite missions at hand (in our case, the Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer - 2, AMSR2). We will use a modified version of the “Wentz” parametric ocean Radiative Transfer Model (RTM) [4] to simulate AMSR2 TBs at key microwave frequencies (Ku- and Ka-band) from the geophysical input of the CMEMS models (for the SIC and sea-ice type) and of the ECMWF numerical weather prediction (NWP) system (the atmosphere that lies between the surface and the satellite). The first step is to improve the way sea-ice emissivity values are entered in the model, and make this emissivity dependent on sea-ice type, which will borrow from the dynamic tie-point methodology of the OSI SAF and CCI SIC algorithms [5]. The observation operator will then be interfaced to the Ensemble Kalman-Filter (EnKF) data assimilation (DA) system of the CMEMS Arctic Marine Forecasting Center, and DA experiments subsequently performed to assess the impact of TB assimilation on SIC and sea-ice type analysis and forecast.

4. **Iceberg forecasting**

More accurate sea ice edge and ensemble forecasts of ocean currents will be beneficial to iceberg forecasting. As a first step, an iceberg drift simulation module is being included in the OpenDrift package that can use the latest Copernicus forecasts of all the forces driving the drift of an iceberg: ocean currents, tides, winds, sea ice and waves [8]. The

OpenDrift software is containerized, meaning that it can be used on cloud solutions such as WeKEO, the data access system where different Copernicus products are efficiently accessible, thus removing intensive downloading operations.

Near real-time remote sensing of icebergs will also be expanded spatially from the Greenland Sea out to the Barents Sea using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) from the Sentinel-1 satellite series as well as several Copernicus Contributing Missions from international sources. The numerical model will be used to fast forward the map of possible iceberg targets from the satellite images and provide an iceberg-risk forecast map. Individual iceberg forecasts will also be provided on demand for users in the field using the IceWatch mobile app. Once an iceberg is spotted, the picture location and time can be fed into the forecast model and a number of possible trajectories sent back to the user. Experienced users familiar with safety protocols in the vicinity of icebergs [9] can receive a free GPS-tracking buoy from ACCIBERG and contribute to the calibration of the forecast model.

5. Conclusion

ACCIBERG is developing improved capabilities for the Copernicus Services through enhanced remote sensing and forecasting techniques. These Copernicus data services are all freely available and open. Users of the Copernicus Services will thus be able to consult forecasts of sea ice accompanied by their uncertainties from short-range to seasonal scale. The demonstration period for iceberg forecasting is planned for Summer 2024 and we are welcoming beta-testers willing to take part in iceberg tagging activities to join our advisory team. The work is paving the way towards the optimal exploitation of future Copernicus Sentinel Expansion missions: Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer (CIMR) for PMW imaging of sea ice, and Copernicus L-band SAR (ROSE-L) with an improved iceberg detection capacity.

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